

Flowering on 1-10 Nov indicates that most varieties have critical photoperiod longer (12-12.5 h) than those of Thai, Burmese, and Vietnamese varieties. For

this reason, most Bangladesh photoperiod-sensitive varieties flower too early if planted in Thailand and in similar latitudes. On the other hand, the

introduced photoperiod-sensitive varieties flower later than Bangladesh varieties because their critical photoperiod is shorter. □

Grain yield and duration of ratoon rice varieties

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To evaluate ratoon performance, we measured grain yield and duration of 10 short- and medium-duration rice varieties during 1984-85 at ACRI.

The main as well as ratoon crop received 100-22-41.5 kg NPK/ha. Immediately after rice harvest, ratoon stubbles were cleaned. Irrigation was given from day 3 onwards. All P and K plus half of N was applied 7 d after cutting. The balance of N was applied in 2 splits on day 25 (maximum tillering) and day 35 (panicle initiation).

Ratoon crop yields varied from 0.43 to 2.20 t/ha (see table). Bhavani's high

Grain yield and duration of ratoon rice. Madurai, India, 1984-85.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)			Crop duration (d)	
	Main planted crop	Ratoon	Ratoon yield compared with planted crop yield (%)	Planted crop	Ratoon
Bhavani	2.5	2.2	86.6	128	78
Ponni	1.7	0.4	27.2	138	88
Puduvai Ponni	2.4	0.8	31.5	138	66
IR20	3.0	0.9	30.7	128	77
ACM8	0.8	0.7	80.0	120	67
ACM9	3.6	1.2	34.6	104	81
ACM10	2.9	1.6	54.3	104	81
CO43	2.6	0.7	25.9	135	69
CO44	2.0	0.9	46.6	120	81
MDU2	2.6	0.5	17.9	138	77
LSD (P=0.05)	0.5				

^aYellowing disease reduced yields.

yield of 2.2 t/ha was 86.6% of main crop yield. Ratoon crop durations varied from 69 to 81 d. Bhavani's field duration was 128 d in the main crop and 78 d in

ratoon crop. Analysis showed no significant correlation between ratoon crop grain yield and duration. □

Hybrid rice in rainfed environments

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Two hybrids (IR46830A/IR9761-19-1R and IR54752A/IR46R) and their parents were dry seeded (75 kg/ha) and grown under strictly rainfed conditions in lowland and upland fields of IRRI in 1987 wet season. IR46, one of the parents, was the check variety. Urea (90 kg N/ha) was topdressed on 17 Sep. Water deficit occurred 45 to 60 d after seeding (DAS) with a maximum stress of 69 kPa soil moisture tension at 20 cm soil depth and 5 kPa at 60 cm.

The table shows the performance of the F₁ hybrids and their parents under rainfed conditions. Hybrid IR46830A/IR9761-19-1R yielded

Yield and yield components of 2 F₁ hybrid rices and their parents under rainfed environments. IRRI, 1987.

Entry	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	100-grain weight (g)	Filled grains (%)	Harvest index
<i>Lowland site</i>					
IR46830A/IR9761-19-1R (F ₁)	3.2	1118	1.90	62.62	0.30
IR9761-19-1	0.7	788	1.28	57.05	0.18
IR46830	2.4	986	1.78	62.19	0.30
IR54752A/IR46R (F ₁)	2.2	716	2.13	56.67	0.20
IR46	2.3	926	2.03	72.09	0.28
IR54752	1.7	574	2.30	62.73	0.20
LSD (0.05)	0.4	320	0.20	22.50	0.06
<i>Upland site</i>					
IR46830A/IR9761-19-1R (F ₁)	1.0	970	1.93	64.28	0.30
IR9761-19-1	0.6	794	1.73	42.75	0.30
IR46830	0.5	910	1.65	46.60	0.23
IR54752A/IR46R (F ₁)	0.8	522	2.15	69.80	0.20
IR46	0.6	492	1.90	69.20	0.23
IR54752	0.8	490	2.20	62.50	0.25
LSD (0.05)	0.3	220	0.18	14.66	0.08

highest with 105% midparent heterosis for the lowland trial and 78% for the upland trial. Hybrid IR54752A/IR46R,

exhibited only 7% and 8% midparent heterosis in the 2 trials and yielded as much as did IR46.

The high yield of IR46830A/IR9761-19-1R was attributed to a high number of panicles. It showed midparent heterosis for all characters at both sites.

Results indicate that hybrids developed specifically for irrigated lowland can be grown under rainfed conditions and still exhibit heterosis

even when subjected to water deficit. Results further suggest that hybrid rices can be developed for rainfed environments. □

Grain quality and nutritional value

Modified method for apparent amylose content (AC) of milled rice

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Colorimetric amylose assay based on amylose standard alone overestimates AC of milled rice because of amylopectin-iodine complex interference at acid pH. Addition of amylopectin (waxy rice starch, 0.6% amylose) to amylose in the standard mixture lowers amylose values, particularly for high-amylose rice. These values are probably closer to true AC since the potato amylose standard is only 80% pure.

Amylose values, however, are expressed on milled rice basis of about 90% starch. Recently, starches of high-amylose indica rices were shown to have the same true AC (about 18%) as low-amylose japonica rices. The increased iodine-blue color was due mainly to

Apparent AC of defatted milled rice flour in pH 4.5-4.8 acetate buffer based on amylose standard and amylose-amylopectin standard with starch content calculated to 90% and 70% of milled rice. IRRRI, 1988.

Variety name	Apparent AC (%) based on		
	Amylose alone	Amylose + amylopectin to	
		90% starch	70% starch
IR29	8.2	0.6	1.9
IR2071-137-5	16.2	9.2	10.6
IR24	19.9	13.2	14.6
IR64	28.2	22.0	23.4
IR8	32.2	26.2	27.6
Mean	20.9	14.2	15.6

*Standard: amylose 0-30 mg/100 ml; amylose: amylopectin 0-30: 90-60 mg/100 ml for 90% starch or 0-30: 90-40 mg/100 ml for 70% starch with defatted milled rice standards at 100 mg/100 ml.

high-iodine binding amylopectin; thus, apparent AC of high-amylose rice starches is 25-26%. High-amylose rice amylopectin has iodine complexing properties different from waxy rice amylopectin, while waxy and low-amylose rice amylopectins are similar in branching properties.

Because classification of milled rice AC into low (10-20%), intermediate (20-25%), and high (>25%) is well accepted and documented, we propose maintaining such classification but calling it apparent AC.

These values can be obtained for defatted rice flour in the amylose-amylopectin standard method by

adjusting starch level (amylose + amylopectin) from 90% to 70% of the milled rice weight. Adding a constant correction factor, 1.4%, to all amylose values based on the 90% starch standard maintains the above classification scheme (see table). With this method, calibration is at pH 4.5-4.8 in acetate buffer, reducing errors inherent in the Williams procedure at alkaline pH. Excess iodine characterizes the acid pH procedure as reflected in the greenish amylose-iodine solution. Defatting with refluxing 95% ethanol gives more accurate apparent amylose values than using undefatted samples, because fat contents of samples are not necessarily identical at similar milling conditions.

The detailed procedure is available upon request. □

Grain characteristics of traditional Basmati varieties of northwest India

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We collected 23 traditional Basmati varieties from northwest India and

studied their grain characteristics (see table).

We divided varieties into two groups. Varieties of group A—HBC-5 (Havana Basmati collection), HBC-85, Pakistani Basmati (Amritsar), Basmati Kota, and Karnal local—have a growth duration of 145-150 d, and are phenotypically similar to Karnal local, which fetches the highest prices in the domestic and export markets.

Grain characteristics of Basmati varieties, India.

Character	Group A (n = 5)			Group B (n = 18)		
	Range	Mean	SEM	Range	Mean	SEM
Milled rice length (mm)	1.00 - 7.35	1.20	0.062	6.17 - 6.87	6.51	0.041
Brown rice (% of rough rice)	78.20 - 79.40	78.74	0.235	78.60 - 80.50	79.80	0.128
Total milled rice (% of rough rice)	65.30 - 67.70	66.72	0.533	65.80 - 68.80	67.31	0.198
Head rice (% of rough rice)	32.20 - 42.50	38.14	1.873	25.10 - 58.50	47.24	1.846
Milled rice breadth (mm)	1.74 - 1.78	1.76	0.008	1.69 - 1.89	1.81	0.013
Length-to-breadth ratio	4.02 - 4.13	4.08	0.018	3.15 - 3.84	3.56	0.037
Length of cooked grain (mm)	13.90 - 15.00	14.55	0.198	12.20 - 14.00	13.26	0.127
Elongation ratio	1.89 - 2.12	2.02	0.042	1.89 - 2.19	2.04	0.021
Alkali spreading value	3.80 - 5.00	4.28	0.224	3.00 - 4.00	3.46	0.087
Amylose content (%)	21.00 - 23.00	22.00	0.316	21.00 - 23.50	21.86	0.212